

SECTION 6.

**INNOVATIVE VECTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT
OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES**

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**THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE PHILOSOPHY
OF SCIENCE IN THE SPHERE
OF SAFETY AND RISK**

***Abstract.** The issue of creating conceptual foundations for the interrelationship between safety and danger is extremely relevant. The philosophy of science can be effectively applied in the study of such a complex and multidimensional*

category as safety, since defining the basic formulations in the study of potential risk is accompanied by a number of difficulties directly related to the uniqueness and multifaceted nature of the phenomenon of safety itself.

In order to minimize the manifestation of dangers in any sphere of human activity, it is necessary to develop a clear conceptual framework for the relationship between safety, danger, and the probability of their occurrence. This will make it possible to understand the nature of risks, assess them in a timely manner, and develop effective mechanisms for human protection within society and the industrial environment.

The article outlines research directions that involve analyzing the essence of human life safety. The peculiarities of the interrelationship between safety and danger in modern society are identified. The issue of substantiating the need to form an effective state security model based on the principles of sustainable development is proposed to be resolved through the creation of a national safety culture.

Keywords: safety, danger, life safety, potential risk, state security model, concept of sustainable development, safety culture

Introduction. The issue of establishing a conceptual framework for the relationship between safety and danger is extremely relevant, as humanity constantly faces new challenges and threats both in everyday life and in the industrial environment. Industrial accidents and environmental disasters, military conflicts, and information risks, as well as global crises, require not only practical solutions but also a deep theoretical understanding of the very nature of safety and danger. It is the philosophy of science that will allow us to form a holistic understanding of risk as a unique safety phenomenon. Subsequently, it will be possible to identify the patterns of its occurrence and assess any type of risk that may affect individuals, society, and the environment. The relevance of the topic lies in the need to develop effective approaches to forecasting, preventing, and minimizing dangers in various spheres of human life, as the complexity of technical systems will only increase with the development of our technogenic civilization.

Article Purpose. The purpose of the study is to analyze the essence of human life safety, to determine the peculiarities of the relationship between safety and danger in modern society, and to substantiate the necessity of

forming an effective state security model based on the principles of sustainable development, safety culture, and the protection of the vital interests of individuals and society.

Results. The philosophy of science can be effectively applied when studying a category as complex and multidimensional as safety. Defining key concepts in the study of potential risks is accompanied by a number of difficulties directly related to the uniqueness and multifaceted nature of the phenomenon of safety itself. To minimize the occurrence of dangers in any sphere of human life, it is necessary to establish a clear conceptual framework for the relationship between safety, danger, and the probability of their occurrence. Such an approach will allow for a deeper understanding of the nature of risks, their timely assessment, and the development of effective mechanisms for human protection in society and in the industrial environment.

Even the simplest organisms possess self-preservation mechanisms. These mechanisms manifest as the ability to distinguish between negative and positive external factors [1]. At higher levels of biological development, a certain extraordinary biological significance begins to emerge. This occurs when a living organism projects meaning that is significant to it onto the surrounding world. And with the emergence of consciousness, mental forms of understanding the environment begin to develop.

Higher-order living beings (animals) possess an important ability: the capacity not only to perceive individual objects holistically but also to assess situations in their environment as a whole. It is precisely thanks to this ability that their behavior is proactive, allowing them to respond in advance to potential threats and avoid dangerous situations. This ability indicates that the foundation for the very concept of safety lies in a living organism's ability to assess the likelihood of negative consequences arising from external influences. Safety, when viewed in this sense, emerges not merely as a state of protection, but as a specific mode of interaction between an organism and the environment in which it exists.

By drawing parallels between any external influence and potential future consequences, an individual organism independently assigns specific meaning to observed phenomena and, through this process, forms an understanding of the likelihood of danger. It is precisely this understanding of potential threats that is crucial for the survival of a living being and

its adaptation to its environment. If an organism does not perceive the surrounding world in the context of potential dangers, it will be unable to respond to threats in a timely manner and will ultimately perish. Thus, the ability to anticipate danger is one of the most important conditions for the survival of any living being.

In human life, the uniqueness of the phenomenon of safety is further developed and takes on a more complex nature. Every individual possesses consciousness and developed thinking from birth [2]. Thus, humans are capable not only of assessing the negative impact on themselves or other elements of their environment, but also of analyzing their own condition in relation to potential dangers. Humans are capable of predicting the consequences of their own actions, as well as modeling potential risks and creating means of protection against them. That is why safety in human society is becoming more than just a natural need. Safety is becoming an important social value that determines the very conditions of existence and development, as well as the preservation of life for the individual and human society as a whole.

The uniqueness of a phenomenon such as safety arises as a specific way of defining the existence of any object in relation to a potential danger. In the human mind, the uniqueness of the phenomena of potential danger and safety are identical. Depending on the circumstances, only the attitude toward these concepts changes. Regarding the emergence of potential danger, in the vast majority of cases, a negative attitude is formed in the human mind in advance. Regarding the uniqueness of the phenomenon of safety, there is a relationship between the object itself (the individual) and the potential positive or negative impact on it.

A review of numerous scientific studies allows us to assert that the phenomenon of safety is unique. The understanding of these concepts has a dual nature in terms of how they are perceived by any individual. In its generality, the essence of safety constitutes the nature of things. In an objective sense, safety is synonymous with the preservation of the natural essence of existence. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the fact that any denial of the essence of the nature of things is potentially dangerous. Therefore, the objective viewpoint is that the safety of things will be determined to a greater extent by their nature [3].

The concept of sustainable development of human society forms the basis of the science of human security [4]. The main tenets of this international concept include a number of assertions regarding the unique nature of security. And they include the following definition of life safety for the population of any country, which is based on the long-term process of sustainable development of the individual person and is not ensured exclusively by armaments or military force. Likewise, the safety of the life and health of every individual should primarily be considered as a component of the development of the cultural and spiritual sphere of society, and only afterward as a component of the socio-political, material-production, and everyday spheres.

The current state of rapid development of our technogenic civilization, along with the transformation and sometimes complete replacement of technologies, gives the issue of ensuring life safety particular importance. Human society is increasingly confronted with challenges that are multi-component in nature. That is why the concept of sustainable development defines safety not only as a state of protection of a person from dangers. The very attitude toward safety and danger is also being renewed.

The concept of sustainable development was created with the aim of establishing a balance among the economic, social, and environmental components of public life. In this context, safety is regarded as the result of effective interaction between the state, civil society, and the individual. An important aspect of this is the formation of a safety culture, which includes a whole set of components. Such a culture of safety is created on the basis of a system of knowledge, moral values, norms of behavior, and the responsible attitude of every individual toward their own life and the lives of others. A high level of safety culture will contribute to reducing the risks of dangerous situations and will thus ensure the population's readiness to act adequately in emergency circumstances. A high level of safety culture will become the driving force for the implementation of sustainable development concepts, since such readiness will not arise by itself or through coercion.

In ensuring life safety, the educational environment plays a particularly important role. It is during the educational process that an individual develops safe behavior skills. In the course of learning, each person gradually develops,

in their own way, environmental awareness, the ability to make well-founded decisions, and the capacity for critical thinking. Our own teaching experience allows us to say that an educated person (in the broad sense of this expression) adapts more easily to changes in the surrounding socio-technical environment. An informed person responds more effectively to threats, which contributes to the development of a safe society. At the same time, it is important not only for an individual to acquire professional competencies, but also to cultivate spiritual and humanistic values, which form the foundation for the harmonious coexistence of people.

By their nature, sciences are either fundamental or applied [5]. Life safety is an applied science that studies the means and methods for ensuring the safety of every individual. This science is directly related to practice and aimed at solving specific problems. In this context, all fundamental branches of knowledge – such as physics, chemistry, and biology – are applied. When it comes to the practical application of the aforementioned scientific principles of life safety, a paradoxical phenomenon arises. On the one hand, the rapid development of technology creates new opportunities for significantly improving the quality of life of humanity as a whole, yet the expected result does not occur. Moreover, technogenic threats are increasing in both scale and consequences, and new occupational risks are emerging within the industrial environment.

Equally important is the consideration of national specificity when creating a model of state security as a whole. Every country has unique historical, cultural, economic, and social conditions of development that are inherent only to that particular state. These characteristics influence the formation of the national security system. An effective security model requires a competent combination of international experience with established national security practices and the needs arising within society.

Conclusions.

Safety challenges themselves arise from an individual's interaction with the environment. Human safety is a general category that characterizes the safeguarding of an individual's life in any country. And a growing understanding of the unique phenomenon of safety will contribute to the creation of such a safety model based on a series of unique components specific to our country.

References:

1. Energy Strategy of Ukraine. <https://mev.gov.ua/reforma/enerhetychna-stratehiya>.
2. Про Цілі сталого розвитку України на період до 2030 року, 722/2019, 2019 р. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/722/2019#Text>
3. Зябіна Є. А., Пимоненко Т. В. Енергетична політика України: ефективність та напрями її підвищення. Економічний простір, 2020. № 160. С. 55–60. <https://doi.org/10.32782/2224-6282/160-10>
4. Nuclear Generation by Country. <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/facts-and-figures/nuclear-generation-by-country>
5. History of Energy in Ukraine. <https://mev.gov.ua/en/storinka/history-energy-ukraine>
6. Завербний А. С., Осадча Н. В. Оцінювання значення, життєздатності та перспектив розвивання атомної енергетики у реалізуванні післявоєнної енергетичної стратегії України: соціально-економічний аспект. *Вісник економічної науки України*, 2024. С. 168-174. [https://doi.org/10.37405/1729-7206.2024.2\(47\)](https://doi.org/10.37405/1729-7206.2024.2(47))
7. Промислова екологія : навч. посіб. / С. О. Апостолюк, В. С. Джигирей, І. А. Соколовський та ін. 2-ге вид., виправл. і доповн. К. : Знання, 2012. 430 с. (Вища освіта XXI століття).
8. Recycling Nuclear Waste: A Win-Win or a Dangerous Gamble? Yale Environment 360. Published at the Yale School of the Environment, 2025. <https://e360.yale.edu/features/nuclear-waste-recycling>
9. Alinejad, S., Khoshsepehr, Z., Alimohammadlou, M. Strategic nuclear waste management for reducing environmental Impacts: Innovative decomposed fuzzy methods. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2025. Vol. 513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145728>